

SIL

International
Society of Limnology

news

ISSUE
82

JULY 2023

LIMNOLOGY.ORG

**The New Brian Moss Student
Competition** Page 4

**Opinion: The Future of the World's
Waters is Indigenous** Page 9

The Tonolli Memorial Fund
Page 20

Boats on the shores of Lake Victoria, Sindo Beach, Kenya. Photo by Michael Maina

The President

WHY AND HOW SHOULD SIL BE ENGAGING IN WATER-RELATED ADVOCACY?

A few months ago, the UN 2023 Water Conference in New York provided a response to the global water crisis around a common goal: tackling the water crisis and achieving Sustainable Development Goal 6 – Clean Water and Sanitation. If we fail to achieve SDG 6, we risk the failure of almost all the other 16 Goals, including those related to food and nutrition, poverty reduction, human health, gender equality, energy, economic growth, sustainable cities, climate change and the environment. The key outcome of the UN 2023 Water Conference, the [Water Action Agenda](#), captured over 700 commitments aimed at driving transformation from a global water crisis to a water-secure world. On World Water Day (22nd of March), UNESCO reaffirmed that water is a vital and common good of humanity, which must therefore be considered on the scale of humanity.

I think we all agree that secure water provision is one of the central tasks to achieve sustainable human development. However, has SIL, our global society of limnologists, engaged in these actions? Is SIL prominent in any advocacy on water issues, helping to transform the world towards water security for everyone? SIL members may argue that the science of limnology is what we contribute to sustainability. While we strive to understand the interactions between the global water cycle and the ecology of particular aquatic ecosystems, we provide the basis for the management of water resources. And as researchers, we are obligated to provide objective facts, while the evaluation of our data and transformation into actions is part of the duties of political actors. I have defended this passive advisory position for quite some time during my career as a scientist, and I assume many of you share a similar opinion. However, in recent years, I have started to question this position, and I am uncertain whether we, as individual researchers and SIL members, should just continue describing the water crisis and its consequences on ecological systems, without actively communicating and engaging in public partnership and advocacy for change. I candidly share my doubts with you, to stimulate a discussion about the role SIL and SIL members could potentially play as an international ally together with other institutions that already play an advocacy role.

There are several reasons why I think SIL has to become more active, despite the historical tradition of being primarily a scientific society. First, it is obvious that research on aquatic systems is dependent on the existence of aquatic systems. Global change

has induced not only dramatic modifications of the functioning of these systems, but has also induced the temporary or even permanent loss of freshwater bodies, from small ponds and ditches, to rivers and large lakes. Second, description and functional understanding has always been only one part of the science of limnology, while the other parts have been advice and guidance to ecosystem management. Looking back to the work of our SIL founders A. Thienemann and E. Naumann 100 years ago, the combination of basic and applied science was one of the hallmarks of the new scientific discipline of limnology. Third, the tradition to study aquatic systems to facilitate their better management is one of the strongest motivations for researchers in many parts of the world where clean drinking water and other ecosystem services are scarce. Hence, if SIL wants to be seriously supporting young researchers from developing economies, we need to expand our focus of limnological work towards water security issues, because SIL can provide an extensive and inclusive platform for exchange and learning. Finally, even the most excellent limnologist engaged in basic research may strongly benefit from exchanges with experts from outside the box, for example with respect to water management challenges, to social motivations that drive human decisions, or to research in the fields of sanitation or infrastructure that can massively affect the sustainable use of water and therefore the ecological integrity of water resources. All these links imply that a limnological society nowadays also has to address topics that are related to water availability and security. However, I ponder if this automatically means that SIL has also to engage in partnerships and advocacy as a priority?

Advocacy is an activity that aims to influence decisions within political, economic, and social institutions by using facts, relationships, the media, and messaging to educate government officials and the public. Partnerships can be seen as an effective tool to promote advocacy. Research and academic institutions, such as SIL, are often relied on only as knowledge generators and brokers, and may help to underpin science and evidence-based decision making. However, they also can play prominent roles in education and capacity development through partnerships in developing countries. What are the avenues in which SIL and SIL members can contribute to tackling the global water crisis?

First, there is an urgent need to make water-related

data freely accessible. Environmental data are considered a major gap in water-related knowledge, and water quality data remain sparse, especially at the global level, in large part due to weak monitoring and reporting capacity. Partnerships have always been central to improving this knowledge and many ongoing and recent initiatives are playing important roles. An example is [World Water Quality Alliance](#), a multi-disciplinary partnership, which provides a participatory platform for water quality monitoring and assessments. We may explore how we can link the numerous environmental data our members have generated to these organizations that explicitly focus

“All these links imply that a limnological society nowadays also has to address topics that are related to water availability and security.”

on water security. Easy and unrestricted access to relevant data is essential to make informed decisions on water resources and water-related risk management.

Second, education and capacity building are crucial to accelerate the development and adoption of more sustainable water management. These activities involve the sharing of knowledge and skills, as based on partnerships between instructors and learners, institutions, and other providers and recipients of information. The increased flexibility and accessibility of digital platforms also present new opportunities for education, in particular for women and minority group members. Furthermore, there is increasing awareness that scientific knowledge needs to be better integrated with local and indigenous knowledge. This is particularly relevant for water. Many textbooks and e-learning materials mostly use data and examples from northern temperate regions, while hydro-meteorological, climate and limnological conditions are very different in the global South, where water security is most severely threatened and capacity is often limited. SIL may explore partnerships that focus on knowledge co-creation instead of knowledge transfer to embrace the diversity of expertise and

experience. The co-development of a systematic, comparative limnology via joint activities of experts from all global regions may be the type of partnership that addresses the worldwide needs to manage the water crisis.

Finally, ecosystems play a central role in regulating water availability and its quality. Hence, SDG [Target 6.6 \(protect and restore water-related ecosystems\)](#) was included under SDG 6, as both a descriptor of sustainability and enabler of all the other SDG 6 targets. Climate, environment and water are intrinsically linked and so are the climate change, environmental change and sustainable water development agendas. The links between water and climate or environment include a greater diversity of stakeholders and potential partners than any other water domain. Science-based joint solutions and innovation, including open science, citizen science, international collaboration, women and youth-led initiatives, as well as traditional and indigenous knowledge, may achieve more climate-resilient water management. Partnerships and cooperation, at all levels, improve water governance and decision-making and stimulate innovative solutions. These interdependencies result in water and environment interventions delivering co-benefits across multiple development goals. SIL as a society may explore whether the engagement in multistakeholder platforms may help strengthen the water development agendas by providing the science-based insight into the links between water availability and climate change. An active entity in this sphere is the [World Water Council](#), an international platform orga-

nization, which focuses on the political dimensions of water security, adaptation and sustainability, with the mission to mobilize action on critical water issues by engaging people in debate and challenging conventional thinking.

As SIL president, it is my responsibility and desire to stimulate discussions on and participation in the transformation of our society towards addressing sustainability more explicitly. I welcome comments and opinions on my thoughts, and would like to hear your ideas and initiatives, how SIL can become more active in the advocacy and partnership to achieve Sustainable Development Goal 6 – Clean Water and Sanitation. Beyond the imminent focus on SDG 6, further ecosystem services or Nature Contributions to People (NCPs) such as food security provided by inland fisheries, aquatic biodiversity, recreation, or spirituality may likewise benefit from our advocacy work for freshwater ecosystems.

We will be soliciting member contributions on this topic in the coming months and we encourage each of you be an active contributor to this discussion.

[Further reading.](#)

Thomas Mehner
SIL President

IN THIS ISSUE

SILnews	2
Letter from the President	2
Next SIL Congress	3
The New Brian Moss Student Competition	4
The Robert G. Wetzel Travel Awards	5
Japan	6
Switzerland	6
Book Presentation - River Culture	7
News from Members	8
Opinion	9
Limnology Around the World	11
Kenya	11
Norway	14
Serbia	16
The Tonolli Memorial Fund	20
Argentina	20
Faces of SIL	22
France	22
India	22
New Zealand	23
Türkiye/Spain	23
Obituary	24
Arnold Nauwerck	24

Next SIL Congress

The next [37th Congress of Society International of Limnology](#) to be held in Brazil (5-9 May 2024), aims to celebrate the temporal and spatial bridges between indigenous and non-indigenous people the world over. The historical break of these bridges has exasperated the isolation and marginalization of indigenous people, worsened the consequences of climate change and accelerated an unprecedented degradation of our landscape.

Join us in the next SIL Congress in Brazil, celebrating indigenous lands the world over! Indigenous peoples, with an ancestral role as guardians of aquatic ecosystems and biodiversity, are safeguarding these resources for future generations as a gift and a hope for the future.

Welcome to Brazil! Welcome to indigenous earth!

Logo of the 37th SIL Congress representing the infinity symbol in a drop and Latin American and the Caribbean sustained by indigenous knowledge, here represented by graphism.

In this issue SIL's President T. Mehner invites us to reflect on SIL's and every limnologist's role in addressing water sustainability. Students will be interested in some changes to the Brian Moss Student Competition, and two Wetzel Travel Award recipients share their experience at SIL100-Berlin. Check out the logo for the next SIL congress in Brazil and a fantastic downloadable book on River Culture.

This issue's Opinion article outlines the role of Indigenous peoples in protecting our waters. From the Limnology Around the World section, we can learn more about the African Great Lakes, unexpected consequences of water browning, and what is happening in the Danube. We have another great Tonolli Report and please meet four of our members in the FACES of SIL section. Unfortunately, we have lost another outstanding limnologist, Arnold Nauwerck.

Hope you enjoy this issue of SILnews.

Giovanna Flaim,
Editor SILnews

Contribution deadline for the January 2024 issue: **01 October, 2023**
Send to: SILnews Editor at SILnews@limnology.org

The New Brian Moss Student Competition

As you have probably read in SILnews Issue 80, the SIL Student Competition has been re-named the “Brian Moss Student Competition” and we are now moving to the fifth edition in connection with the 2024 SIL congress in Brazil. This award has attracted much interest from SIL student members with participants from 31 countries in the last edition. As before, there will be two stages of selection, one at the national and one at the international level. Students interested in participating should submit their documents (opened on May 1, 2023) to their National SIL Representative in the country where they are doing their thesis or have been enrolled in a graduate program. The National Representatives of SIL will then establish a domestic jury of qualified researchers to select the best article to compete in the next stage. Only one article per country will be selected, independent of country membership size. The articles selected will then enter the second round of competition at the international level. At this stage, 10 jurors, all editors or members of editorial boards of recognized international journals related to freshwater ecology will select the best article to receive the Brian Moss Student Award.

At both stages, the same criteria for ranking the papers will be applied. These are 1) scientific quality of the study including methodology and experimental approach (if any), 2) originality of the research question

or hypothesis tested, and 3) relevance and potential scientific impact of the publication including its contribution to conservation and/or restoration of inland waters at local, landscape, or continental scales. Regarding criterion 3, we will request in the application form that the student specifically addresses this point. We have also introduced equal weights for all three criteria.

Another improvement to the competition is that we have made a major effort in selecting members of the International Jury that will not only consider editorial experience, but also gender balance and global representation of the jurors (Fig. 1).

Finally, we would like to recognize the merit of all students participating in the national and international competitions and, therefore, we will (with their approval) publish the names of all participants on the SIL website and via social media.

Ruben Sommaruga (Chair)
Angeles González Sagrario (Vice-Chair)
SIL Brian Moss Student Competition

Find the announcement [here](#) and the application form [here](#).

Fig. 1 Location of members of the International Jury for the next edition of the “Brian Moss Student Award”.

The Robert G. Wetzel Travel Awards

The Robert G. Wetzel Memorial Fund is used for travel support for young limnologists who are presenting papers at SIL congresses. For the SIL100 Congress – Berlin Xin Liu (Japan) and Benjamin Misteli (Switzerland) were among eight recipients of the Wetzel Travel awards. Here are their reports.

JAPAN XIN LIU

It was my honor to receive the Robert G. Wetzel Memorial Travel Award from the International Society of Limnology (SIL). My sincere gratitude to the selection committee who recommended me for this award, allowing me to participate in the 36th Congress of SIL (SIL2022).

The Congress was held in Germany, commemorating SIL's 100th anniversary and its birthplace. This was my first visit to Berlin, and it was a great honor to attend this conference. I gave an oral presentation titled "Mate-seeking behavior in the calanoid copepod *Eodiaptomus japonicus* from Lake Biwa, Japan". This is the first study investigated the mating behavior of *E. japonicus*, the most important zooplankton species in Lake Biwa. Copepods are known to track mates using chemical and hydromechanical signals. This study showed that *E. japonicus* belongs to hydromechanical-communicating species. Only 6 of the 29 *Eodiaptomus* species including *E. japonicus*, are known to use hydromechanical signals to finding a mate. I introduced details of characteristic mating behavior of this copepod and the implications for reproduction and population strategies. Many researchers were interested in my talk and we had an in-depth conversations and discussions.

In addition to my presentation, I attended many sessions covering a wide range of topics. The most impressive presentation I attended was the keynote lecture given by Professor Thomas Mehner,

President of the SIL Society, titled "Diversity of researcher types and certain philosophical concepts in limnology"*. The mission of limnologists, as conceived by Professor T. Mehner is to promoting excellence in studying and managing inland waters and addressing global issues through the fostering of interdisciplinary approaches and the transfer of knowledge. He mentioned that researchers can be categorized according to their specialty, such as Disciplinary Specialist, Universalist, Operational Manager, Method Expert, Problem Solver, Instructor. Since limnology is a representative interdisciplinary subject and we as humans have limited cognition and energy, various researchers with their specific advantages and cooperation may lead to great achievements. Therefore, diversity of researchers is extremely important for the development of limnology, and contributions to limnological research should not be limited to the number of published papers but other potential aspects. Additionally, I also attended the session "Open dialogue on world water issues and solutions across generations" hosted by Professor Michio Kumagai. In this session, Japanese junior and elementary school students who participated in the Biwako Trust Junior Doctor Training Project gave excellent oral and poster presentations using very fluent English, and I was very impressed to learn about their interesting and meaningful research projects. This conference also provided a good opportunity for me to communicate with young limnologists from many countries such as Germany, the Netherlands, Canada, Japan, China, Brazil, Thailand, Bangladesh, the Philippines. We plan to organize joint research projects related to elucidating freshwater ecosystems and solving environmental problems in the future.

*Mehner T. 2023. *Diversity of researcher types and plurality of philosophical concepts in limnology – an essay. Inland Waters* <https://doi.org/10.1080/20442041.2023.2218985>

SWITZERLAND BENJAMIN MISTELI

As a 3rd year PhD student, I had the bad luck that most of my PhD journey was dominated by travel and work restrictions. While online conferences offer an excellent platform to promote your research and keep up with the research in your field, they only provide little opportunity to meet and interact with colleagues. With the support of the Robert G. Wetzel Memorial Travel Award, I could finally visit an international conference in person, just before the end of my PhD.

I presented some recent results from my PhD studies as an oral presentation entitled “Should they stay or should they go: New insights on the removal of invasive macrophytes from a biodiversity perspective” in the session “Invasive alien species in inland waters: invasion trends, impacts and management”, chaired by Dr. Vadim Panov. These results are part of an international collaboration where we analyzed the effects of the removal of macrophytes on phytoplankton, zooplankton and macroinvertebrates. Removal of macrophytes is cost-intensive, often comes with a low success rate and the impacts of macrophyte removal on the ecosystem are poorly studied. With this study and our project, we want to create a foundation for building a more balanced and sustainable approach for future management strategies. I was glad to present my research in front of such a fantastic crowd at SIL, answer exciting questions and exchange ideas afterwards during the conference.

Besides my talk, I listened to many engaging sessions and plenary talks on a broad range of topics and got exciting insights into already known but also completely new topics. Whilst I enjoyed this scientific part a lot, the biggest highlight for me were the moments outside of the sessions. I arrived in Berlin knowing only a few people, but I left Berlin with the feeling of knowing half of the conference. It was great to meet and talk with all the people I was finally/am collaborating with but never had the chance to meet before, but also with new people, including other PhD students, senior scientists from my field, the SIL board and the editorial board of *Inland waters* where I am an Associate Editor *in training* since last year.

Until I arrived in Berlin, I was unsure if attending the conference was the right choice as I should be writing my PhD thesis. However, after attending, I am sure this was the right choice. Meeting and exchanging with so many great people was a great inspiration and a huge motivation for the upcoming end of my PhD and whatever comes afterwards. Thank you to SIL and especially all the selection committee members for allowing me to receive this travel award. And thank you to everyone who made SIL2022 such a good memory for me!

Some impressions of my time during the conference in pictures: meeting collaborators for the first time and celebrating our recent publication, doing sightseeing and joining a big crowd following a poster presentation.

Book Presentation

RIVER CULTURE: A GLOBAL STUDY EXAMINES THE RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN MAN AND NATURE

It is obvious that humanity, and planet Earth, with all its living beings, are in a severe crisis regarding the equitable and sustainable distribution of natural resources, especially continental water. In nature, exponential processes rarely occur over long periods of time because they are usually rapidly buffered by feedback mechanisms. In the Anthropocene, however, processes such as population growth, dam construction, or per capita demand for water grow exponentially, while the numbers of free-flowing rivers, or biological species or forms of culture tied to water, trend exponentially downward.

The River Culture Concept is an approach to restore harmony between humans and nature in the places where humanity first developed and spread: river valleys. A book just published by UNESCO, *River Culture: Life as a Dance in the Rhythm of Waters*, presents how differently humans and non-human organisms have adapted to the rhythms of natural floods and droughts, what factors promote and threaten this biocultural diversity, what actions can be taken to recover this diversity, and under what socio-cultural circumstances such actions are successfully stimulated and implemented.

The book has been designed to serve as a toolbox of examples, showing how river-related problems can be overcome, and how engaged societal groups have succeeded in implementing sustainable solutions, all over the world. On more than 900 pages, socio-ecological portraits of 28 rivers from 4 continents (Africa: 6, Asia: 7, Americas: 6, Europe: 9) are presented, five reviews summarize sustainable concepts for riverscape management in the Anthropocene, two chapters deal with artist's perspectives for environmental communication and one with gender equality. To make this toolbox available to everyone, authors have engaged a widely comprehensive language, and the electronic versions of all the chapters are freely available (and can be further shared via Creative Commons) at the document repository of UNESCO publishing.

Wantzen KM. (Ed.) 2023. *River Culture: Life as a Dance in the Rhythm of Waters*. UNESCO Publishing, Paris, 901+XV pp, ISBN 978-92-3-100540-4.

The book can be freely downloaded as [single chapters](#) or the [whole book](#).

A short summary is given in: Wantzen KM. 2022. River Culture: socioecology of the rhythm of the waters. The Geographical Journal [DOI: 10.1111/geoj.12476](https://doi.org/10.1111/geoj.12476)

<https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8009447>

About the editor: [Professor Wantzen's](#) expertise covers ecology, biodiversity and human nature-interactions, specifically in freshwater systems and their aquatic-terrestrial interaction zones. After his PhD work at the Max-Planck-Institute of Limnology, he coordinated a research project on the Pantanal wetland at the Federal University of Mato Grosso, Brazil, later, he built up a research group at University of Konstanz. Since 2010, he holds a chair in Restoration Ecology of Aquatic Ecosystems at the University of Tours, and he is member of the Sustainability Cluster (FERED/RISE) at the University of Strasbourg. In 2014, he was nominated "UNESCO Chair Fleuves et Patrimoine", building up a global network on sustainable hydrosystem management (renominated in 2018 and 2022).

News From Members

WILL SOYBEAN TRANSPORT DESTROY THE WORLD'S LARGEST WETLAND?

After being abandoned in 2000 due to ecological, economical, and social concerns, the plan to extend the Hidrovia waterway project to the upper sections of the Paraguay River in Brazil was re-pet on the political agenda by the Bolsonaro regime in 2020 and is being continued by the current government. Despite recent drought years (2019-2022) having made navigation downstream of Corumbá unpassable in large, already dredged river sections, the current plan envisages to dredge and straighten about 700 river km in the shallower upstream section between Corumbá and Cáceres. This would drain and shrink the World's largest wetland, the Pantanal, which is one of the last nearly natural large landscapes in Central and South America. The unique biodiversity, the large populations of rare species, and the traditional people of this seasonal wetland, nominated as UNESCO World Heritage, Biosphere and Ramsar sites, are in acute danger. Rather than building harbors, transportation of soybeans, sugar and other products should be by train.

[Read the full article here.](#)

Photo: opantaneiro.com.br

SAVE WATER, SAVE LAKES.

International Lake Environment
Committee Foundation (ILEC)

International Symposium 2022 "Fostering the Value of Lakes for Future Generations" Report

Date : October 15, 2022 (Sat.) 10:00 - 16:30
Venue : Lake Biwa Museum Hall and Annex, Shiga Prefecture
(Hybrid format with simultaneous interpretation)

International Lake Environment Committee Foundation
(ILEC)

SIL members will definitely be interested in reading the [International Lake Environment Committee \(ILEC\) Report of Fostering the Value of Lakes for Future Generations](#).

Other Reports, Newsletters, Videos, and Presentation Materials are also [available here](#).

Backwater near Orth Austria. Photo by Sabine Wanzenboeck

The Future of the World's Waters is Indigenous

Brazil, Latin American and the Caribbean are Indigenous lands! During the last centuries, Indigenous people have lost territories and rights over the world. These losses have impacted natural resources and the sustainability of Indigenous populations across continents.

The governance of these areas by Indigenous peoples is historically associated with high carbon storage, and greater biodiversity, ecosystem services and water quality (e.g., Fao & Filac, 2021). Therefore, the preservation of the rights of these people is critical to mitigate the consequences of climate change and maintain the quality of human life.

According to ECLAC (2014), there are currently 826 Indigenous peoples living in Latin American and the Caribbean, with a fragmented distribution over the landscape. These communities have managed the soils and waters for centuries, maintaining them in a sustainable way through ancient techniques and tools.

In 2020, the pandemic of COVID 19 exposed the fragility and invisibility of Indigenous peoples across continents. Considered one of the most vulnerable social groups in the world (Lustig & Tommasi, 2020), for Indigenous peoples, pandemics and diseases common in the past are a continuing threat due the absence of public policy and governmental support. Contagious diseases, invasions by mining, murders in several territorial disputes are only some of the threats faced by Indigenous peoples (Fig. 1). Recently, the world has seen the degradation of

the Yanomami peoples' health in the Brazilian Amazon, aggravated by government negligence.

One way to address the very important issue of health has been to invite medical students to Indigenous villages and participate in traditional rituals. Seeing firsthand is fundamental to breaking down prejudices and foster trust. This increases awareness of the role of future doctors in respecting traditional communities and their knowledge, while also providing Indigenous communities the opportunity to participate in public education. Poor health is also a result of their land's invasion, followed by the contamination of aquatic ecosystems by mercury and other heavy metals, deforestation and loss of resilience (Bouton *et al.*, 2022), and the potential reduction of the Amazon role as carbon sink (Gatti *et al.*, 2021).

Human pressures have changed the world and converted numerous natural ecosystems into unproductive areas. The Anthropocene age is characterized by human activity that has reached the highest indexes in our history and tipping points has become a reality in several ecosystems, indicating abrupt shifts and untold risks for natural resources (e.g., Dakos *et al.*, 2019). In this regard, Indigenous land along with cultural memory and identity represent a great advantage for biodiversity and ecosystem conservation. Indigenous peoples are the guardians of 22% of the world's areas, responsible for protecting approximately 80% of our biodiversity (Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations, [FAO](#)). According to FAO, indigenous people represent only 6% of the planet's population, with most living in middle-income countries and 19% associated with the extreme poor countries. This paradoxical condition is completely incompatible with the current biodiversity crisis and the role of the Indigenous knowledge in conservation of the landscapes.

In the face of crisis scenarios, Indigenous people need

Fig. 1 The mining murder and deforestation by Ibraim Nascimento, Afro-Brazilian visual artist and activist.

Fig. 2 Ibraim Nascimento and Minister of Indigenous People, Sônia Guajajara, in political manifestation against environmental devastation and violence against Indigenous peoples. Sônia Guajajara is the first Minister of Indigenous People in Brazilian history, and represents the historical fight of these people for rights and lands.

Fig. 3 *Victoria amazonica* in a floodplain on the Solimões River. Indigenous peoples' traditional management influences water quality and biodiversity conservation beyond their own lands (Photo by Bianca Weiss).

to become active participants in public politics involving the discussion of their rights and role in the preservation of their own territory. For the first time in history, the state of Alagoas has instituted the Superintendence of Policies for Indigenous Peoples. The Superintendence, which is part of the State Secretariat for Women and Human Rights (SEMUDH), will be headed by the second author, a Xucuru-Kariri Indigenous person, Maynami José Santana da Silva, from the municipality of Palmeira dos Índios. His role will be to build policies in favor of the traditional peoples of the State and to fight against social and racial inequalities. Under the present Brazilian government, mining in Indigenous lands and protected areas has been curtailed, and plans to combat deforestation in the Amazon and Cerrado biomes have been started (Fig. 2). The Brazilian Limnology Association, along with other scientific societies (e.g., the Brazilian Society for the Advancement of Science) and organizations, highlight the urgent need to support Indigenous peoples in land conservation. According to the United Nations, Indigenous people have a critical role in water preservation due their sustainable and traditional use and governance (UN, 2022). However, access to drinking water and proper sanitation is limited and often associated with the water pollution around Indigenous lands, absence of the projects and politics for Indigenous peoples and governmental insistence in denying Indigenous peoples' relevance when discussing water availability (UN, 2022).

Historically, their isolation, promoted by non-indigenous people, jeopardized their quality of life, spiritual values and culture and the sustainability of ecosystem services for future generations. The traditional use of landscapes represents a heritage for all, a rare indication that humans and biodiversity can coexist in a changing

world, thus avoiding abrupt shifts and turning points. In fact, Indigenous territories with full property rights saw a 66% reduction in annual deforestation compared with land outside their borders (Baragwanatha & Bayi, 2019). Many Indigenous peoples have a strict relationship with natural aquatic ecosystems, contributing to the preservation and sustainable use of aquatic biodiversity. Sometimes this connection with freshwater indicates a strong association with spiritual and cultural identity, reflecting knowledge about seasonal and hydrological cycles (Blackstock, 2001) and ancient management of these aquatic ecosystems, respecting aspects such as ecological resilience and sustained and responsible fishing. In Indigenous nations freshwater is often considered a gift, supporting ecosystem integrity and the dignity of the people as a symbol of sanctity and ancestors' presence (Fig. 3).

Acknowledgements

We thank all Indigenous peoples and their ancestors for their continued efforts in biodiversity conservation. In memory of all Indigenous peoples who have died throughout world history, especially during the COVID 2019 pandemic. Our gratitude to Ibraim Nascimento for putting his art at the service of Indigenous peoples' protection.

References

- Baragwanatha K, Bayi E. 2019. Collective property rights reduce deforestation in the Brazilian Amazon. *PNAS* 117: 20495–20502.
- Blackstock M. 2001. Water: A First Nations' spiritual and ecological perspective. *BC Journal of Ecosystems and Management* 1: 2–14.
- Boulton CA, Lenton TM, Boers N. 2022. Pronounced loss of Amazon rainforest resilience since the early 2000s. *Nature Climate Change* 12: 271–278.
- Dakos V, Matthews B, Hendry AP, *et al.* 2019. Ecosystem tipping points in an evolving world. *Nature Ecology and Evolution* 3: 355–362.
- ECLAC (Economic Commission for Latin America and the Caribbean). 2014. Los pueblos indígenas en América Latina. Avances en el último decenio y retos pendientes para la garantía de sus derechos. Síntesis. Santiago. (also available [here](#)).

FAO & FILAC. 2021. Forest governance by indigenous and tribal peoples. An opportunity for climate action in Latin America and the Caribbean. Santiago. [FAO](#).

Gatti LV, Gloor M, Miller JB, Doughty CE, Malhi Y, *et al.* 2014. Drought sensitivity of Amazonian carbon balance revealed by atmospheric measurements. *Nature* 506: 76–80.

Lustig N, Tommasi M. 2020. [COVID-19 and social protection of poor and vulnerable groups in Latin America: a conceptual framework](#) (accessed 13 March 2023).

UN (United Nations). 2022. Human rights to safe drinking water and sanitation of indigenous peoples: state of affairs and lessons from ancestral cultures. Report of the special rapporteur on the human rights to safe drinking water and sanitation, Pedro Arrojo Agudo. A/HRC/51/24. New York.

<https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8009415>

Authors

VANESSA FE HA Kankaing Indigenous People

Member of Young Limnologists Committee- 37th SIL Congress

Vanessa Fe ha is an indigenous Kaingang from the south of the Atlantic Forest, a journalist, academic and communications coordinator at Arpinsul and the Indigenous Knowledge Portal, and co-founder of the women's collective Ga Jare.

MAYNAMI JOSÉ SANTANA Xucuru-Kariri Indigenous People

Superintendent of Policies for Indigenous Peoples of Alagoas State (Brazil)
Member of Scientific Committee- 37th SIL Congress

In addition to having a postgraduate degree in Law from Universidade Damásio de Jesus and being an activist for the cause of traditional peoples in Alagoas and Brazil, superintendent Maynami is a member of the legal advisory of the Articulation of Peoples and Indigenous Organizations of the Northeast, Minas Gerais and Espírito Santo (APOINME) and former president of the Indigenous Peoples Law Commission (3rd subsection of OAB-AL). He is considered the first indigenous person to work as a lawyer in Alagoas.

LUCIANA GOMES BARBOSA Chair of 37th SIL Congress

Federal University of Paraíba (Brazil)

Luciana holds a Ph.D. (2009) in Ecology, Conservation and Wildlife Management from the Federal University of Minas Gerais. She is Associate Professor at the Federal University of Paraíba, and founder and coordinator of the International Drylands Limnology Network (INLD). Her research focuses on understanding the effects of drought and multiple stressors on biodiversity and resilience in dryland aquatic ecosystems. Luciana is President of the Brazilian Association of Limnology (ABLImno), Coordinator of the Environmental Working Group of the Brazilian Society for the Progress of Science (SBPC). Representative of the SBPC in the National Council for the Environment (CONAMA).

Fig. 4 Meeting of the Akroá Gamella people from Piauí and Maranhão (Brazil) concerning land demarcation.

LIMNOLOGY AROUND THE WORLD: KENYA

Committing to Action for Freshwater Ecosystems and Biodiversity in the African Great Lakes

Kevin Obiero¹, Alfred O. Achieng², Zephaniah A. Migeni³, Stephanie Smith³, Ted Lawrence³ and Matthew McCandless⁴

Email: kevobiero@gmail.com

¹Kenya Marine and Fisheries Research Institute, Kisumu, Kenya

²University of Eldoret, Department of Fisheries and Aquatic Science, Eldoret, Kenya

³African Centre for Aquatic Research and Education, Michigan, United States

⁴International Institute for Sustainable Development, Experimental Lakes Area, Winnipeg, Canada

Introduction

Freshwater ecosystems provide essential services to billions of people worldwide (Lynch *et al.*, 2023). Despite their limited spatial scope (less than 1% of the planet's surface), they host 10% of all species, including a third of all vertebrate species (Tickner *et al.*, 2020). According to the World Wildlife Fund for Nature's Living Planet Report, freshwater species populations have witnessed the greatest overall global decline (83%) over the past 50 years (WWF, 2022). The planet is in the midst of a biodiversity and climate crisis with one third of freshwater populations now threatened with extinction. This is particularly evident in the African Great Lakes (Fig. 1), renowned as "hotspots of biodiversity" (Salzburger *et al.*, 2014) providing essential ecosystem goods and services to over 90 million people (Tebbs *et al.*, 2022).

Scientists studying the African Great Lakes, particularly Lake Victoria, began to notice significant and concerning changes caused by a range of interlinked anthropogenic activities in the early 1900s (Njagi *et al.*, 2022). These interlinked multiple threats include rapid population growth, overfishing, increased land cultivation, harmful algal blooms, non-native invasive species, urban and industrial pollution, eutrophication and, more recently, a rapidly changing ecosystem and biodiversity loss (Plisnier *et al.*, 2022; Achieng *et al.*, 2023). Although these mounting threats are widely recognized and debated, actions to address them have been monumentally slow over the past decades.

In a recent opinion piece, we found out that Africa lags behind in many aspects of biodiversity studies due to biodiversity data deficiency and access (Achieng *et al.*, 2023). Furthermore, insufficient financial

and technical capacity impedes sound policy formulation and implementation for conservation and management. Despite this, very few studies have focused on the interplay between biodiversity and ecosystem change. Additionally, the lack of skilled professionals is a major impediment to data acquisition and design for the execution of high-quality scientific studies in the region. As such, our goal is to ignite the discussion about monitoring biodiversity loss in rapidly changing ecosystems in Africa by emphasizing the need for biodiversity data-driven policy interventions and management implementation in Africa (Achieng *et al.*, 2023). Consequently, there is still much that can be done to help protect freshwater biodiversity, particularly, if people better understand the benefits these plants and animals provide.

Calls to Action

During the recent UN Water Conference—the first of its kind in nearly 50 years—I argued that we can tackle the plethora of issues threatening freshwater supplies and biodiversity if we are willing to work together across 'knowledge silos' and across geographical boundaries to achieve internationally agreed upon water related goals and targets (Obiero, 2023).

The research my team and I have conducting over the past few years has made calls for collective stewardship of these vital aquatic resources for present and future generations through collaboration, knowledge sharing, and harmonization of research and management as critical elements to enhance conservation efforts in the AGL (Obiero *et al.*, 2020; Plisnier *et al.*, 2022). We specifically outlined three potential approaches to realize a long-term, multi-lake harmonized monitoring strategy. In a nutshell, there is need for support from a wide community of researchers and managers, as well as political will and sufficient financial, human, and infrastructural resources and capacities for its implementation (Plisnier *et al.*, 2022).

Independent organizations such as the International Institute for Sustainable Development (IISD) and African Center for Aquatic Research and Education (ACARE), through the African Great Lakes Advisory Group Network, have committed increasing efforts to achieve shared goals for healthy AGL ecosystems through collaborative actions, including: capacity building, standardized data collection protocols, accessible information and data, harmonized research priorities, strengthened networks, and inclusive community engagement strategies.

There is ample evidence that the African Great Lakes region has a strong foundation to sustain economic and population growth in the future and higher levels of prosperity. If decision makers in the African Great Lakes build on these strengths and propose actionable recommendations, working intentionally to foster the productivity and well-being of all riparian communities, the region will innovate and sustain greater prosperity in the future. We call on governments to ensure that the new global framework works for people and nature by prioritizing measures to safeguard freshwater biodiversity.

In February 2023, we hosted the Annual Meeting of the African Great Lakes Stakeholders Network Conference to harness new perspectives for sound research, policy, and management in the African Continent. Here are some of the proposed resolutions and proposed actions by the conference attendees to protect freshwater ecosystems in the AGLs. We committed to:

- 1. Build regional capacity for the African Great Lakes through collaborative courses for scientists, with emphasis on women and early career scientists. We will:**
 - Grow a successful African Women in Science program that fosters gender-balanced science presence and leadership in the AGL region by increasing the number of African women in aquatic science and management leadership positions.
 - o Reach 50-100 African women aquatic scientists through leadership and knowledge-exchange programs.
 - o Develop and grow an East African, scientific Education and Training program to improve field-based and higher education experiences and knowledge in freshwater sciences for long-term sustainability of the African Great Lakes.
 - o Hold collaborative courses for 100+ scientists annually to share knowledge across freshwater lakes.

Fishermen preparing boats for fishing along the northern tip of Lake Turkana in Ethiopia. Photo by Kevin Obiero.

2. Create long-term systems to monitor and improve the health of the African Great Lakes. We will:

- Create and facilitate an accessible and open platform that houses scientific information and data from, and for, the African Great Lakes.
- Develop a long-term monitoring program for the African Great Lakes to understand lake conditions and trends through standardized data collection protocols for information that is

used by scientific, decision-making, and local communities.

- o Develop, implement, and share harmonized water monitoring practices that are based on a standardized template, but tailored to specific countries and regions.
- o Create, implement, and share information and data related to socioeconomic and market surveys, frame surveys, catch assessment surveys and hydroacoustic studies to inform policy decisions.

Fig. 1 The biodiversity rich terrestrial and aquatic ecosystems connectivity in Africa (Achieng *et al.*, 2023).

- o Map geographic areas of research and engagement for the African Great Lakes
- 3. Harmonize research and management priorities for accelerated outcomes for the African Great Lakes. We will:**
- Share information across borders to inform policies and management related to lake, fishery, and community health.
 - Develop a lake wide management plan template that can be customized for different lakes, using successful strategies and technologies.
 - Develop shared research and strategies to solve issues related to: gender equality, climate change resiliency, algal blooms, biodiversity, plastics, aquaculture, and others.
- 4. Strengthen the African Great Lakes network through shared, cross-basin knowledge and action. We will:**
- Facilitate an African Great Lakes scientific network through active lake Advisory Groups to establish region-wide solutions for the African Great Lakes and their communities.
 - o Hold frequent virtual and in-person discussions and exchanges to share information across institutions, borders, and lakes.
 - o Implement projects across countries and lakes.
 - Develop inclusive engagement strategies with and for communities so they understand, support, and take action for healthy lakes and people.
 - o Develop and implement methods, including education and citizen science, that empower communities to engage in water and health issues.

References

Achieng AO, Arhonditsis GB, Mandrak N, Febria C, Opaa B, Coffey TJ, Masese FO, Obiero K, Irvine K, Barasa JE. 2023. Monitoring biodiversity loss in rapidly changing Afrotropical ecosystems: an emerging imperative for governance and research. *Philosophical Transactions of the Royal Society B* 20220271. <https://doi.org/10.1098/rstb.2022.0271> in press.

Lynch AJ, Cooke SJ, Arthington AH, Baigun C, Bossenbroek L, Dickens C, Harrison I, Kimirei I, ... Jähnig SC. 2023. People need freshwater biodiversity. *WIREs Water* e1633. <https://doi.org/10.1002/wat2.1633>

Njagi DM, Routh J, Odhiambo M, Luo C, Basapuram LG, Olago D, Klump V, Stager C. 2022. A century of human-induced environmental changes and the combined roles of nutrients and land use in Lake Victoria catchment on eutrophication. *Science of The Total Environment* 835: 155425. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2022.155425>

Obiero K. 2023. UN Water Conference Should Highlight African Great Lakes. <https://www.cnbc africa.com/2023/un-water-conference-should-highlight-african-great-lakes/>. Published online on CNBC Africa on 20 March 2023.

Obiero K, Lawrence T, Ives J, Smith S, Njaya F, Kayanda R, Kayanda R, Waidbacher H, Olago D, Miriti E, Hecky RE. 2020. Advancing Africa's great lakes research and academic potential: Answering the call for harmonized, long-term, collaborative networks and partnerships. *Journal of Great Lakes Research* 46: 1240–1250.

Plisnier PD, Kayanda R, MacIntyre S, Obiero K, Okello W, Vodacek A, ... Lawrence T. 2022. Need for harmonized long-term multi-lake monitoring of African Great Lakes. *Journal of Great Lakes Research*. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jglr.2022.01.016> in press.

Salzburger W, Van Bocxlaer B, Cohen A S. 2014. Ecology and evolution of the African Great Lakes and their faunas. *Annual Review of Ecology, Evolution, and Systematics* 45: 519-554

Tebbs E, Byrne A, Lomeo D, Thompson H, Owoko W, Nyaga J, Ongore C, Last J, Migeni Z, Everitt L. 2023. Satellite earth observation for the sustainable management of the African Great Lakes. King's College London. https://kclpure.kcl.ac.uk/portal/files/204784035/Tebbs_et_al_2023_PolicyBrief_AfricanGreatLakes.pdf

Tickner D, Opperman JJ, Abell R, Acreman M, Arthington AH, Bunn SE, Cooke SJ, Dalton J, ... Young, L. 2020. Bending the curve of global freshwater biodiversity loss: An emergency recovery plan. *BioScience* 70: 330–342.

WWF. 2022. Living Planet Report 2022 – Building a nature positive society. Almond REA, Grooten M, Juffe Bignoli D, Petersen T. (Eds). WWF, Gland, Switzerland. https://wwflpr.awsassets.panda.org/downloads/lpr_2022_full_report.pdf

<https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8009402>

Sindo Beach along the shores of Lake Victoria, Kenya. Photo by Kevin Obiero

LIMNOLOGY AROUND THE WORLD: NORWAY

Linking Forest to Fish: A Story of Coastal Darkening

Dag O. Hessen¹ and Anders Frugård Opdal²
Email: d.o.hessen@mn.uio.no

¹ Dept. of Biosciences and Centre for Biogeochemistry in the Anthropocene, University of Oslo, Norway

² Dept. of Biological Sciences, University of Bergen, Norway

A prominent trend that has received much attention over the past couple of decades is the phenomenon of freshwater “browning”, or “brownification”, notably in northern lakes and rivers (Creed *et al.*, 2018). The proximate cause of this browning is increased concentrations of highly coloured dissolved organic matter (CDOM) made up of large, complex molecules known as humic acids. These molecules, in turn, originate either directly by leachate from vegetation litterfall or roots with associated mycorrhiza, or indirectly via soils and bogs (Fig. 1). The ultimate drivers are more disputed, yet there is evidence that the main causes are reduced acidification

Fig. 1 Natural dissolved organic carbon in a waterfall draining a boreal forest catchment. Photo by DO Hessen.

(Monteith *et al.*, 2007), changes in land use (Finstad *et al.* 2016; Kritzberg *et al.*, 2020) and changes in climate and hydrology (de Wit *et al.*, 2016). The consequences of this browning are first and foremost increased light attenuation, reducing the depth of photosynthesis (Karlsson *et al.*, 2007; Thrane *et al.*, 2014). Secondly these organic molecules, although quite recalcitrant, also form a substratum for heterotrophic bacteria. Together, these changes drive aquatic systems towards net heterotrophy with less uptake of O₂ and increased emissions of CO₂. In a global climate change perspective this is suggested to have a considerable impact, since

Fig. 2 Glacial erosion and permafrost thaw promote coastal darkening in the high Arctic and are major conduits of CO₂ and CH₄ originating from terrestrially fixed carbon.

northern freshwaters are major conduits of terrestrially fixed carbon to the atmosphere (Tranvik *et al.*, 2009). On top of this, browning also reduces the habitat for visual predators (Aksnes & Utne, 1997), promotes deep water anoxia and increase greenhouse gas emissions.

The impacts of freshwater browning in lakes and streams are manifold, but the journey of the humic acids have just begun. Sooner or later this brown freshwater reaches the coast and mixes with saline coastal waters. Even though bacteria and sunlight have had ample time to oxidize and dismantle these complex humic molecules on their way to the coast, a significant portion remains intact (Fransner *et al.*, 2016). The question is then the fate of this recalcitrant DOM in marine systems; is it flocculated and sinks into the sediments, is it diluted to nearly homeopathic and insignificant concentrations, or may it also pose relevant impacts on marine recipient waters?

Before we add the next link to this chain of events, it is worth mentioning that there are other causal routes that move terrestrial carbon into coastal waters. At high latitudes, progressing permafrost thaw and glacier melt promote fluxes of dissolved and particulate matter of terrestrial origin to coastal areas (Fig. 2). Such fluxes are likely an important driver for the pronounced increase in light attenuation that have been recorded for Svalbard fjords in the high Arctic as revealed by remote sensing over the last 30 years (Konik *et al.*, 2021). Also at lower latitudes, increased export of DOM from land has been associated with reduced coastal water clarity (Martin *et al.*, 2021). Indeed, the phenomenon of gradually increasing coastal water light attenuation due to freshwater influence is so commonly observed, it has been termed “coastal water darkening” (Aksnes *et al.*, 2009).

Returning to the drivers, forest planting and afforestation, notably of coniferous forests, are known to promote carbon export and thus browner and darker freshwaters (Finstad *et al.*, 2016; Kritzberg *et al.*, 2020). The link from increased forest volume to darker waters can be attributed to increased net terrestrial net primary production (NPP), and thus an increased export of dissolved organic matter to surface waters. Also, forest planting on former peatlands promotes export of terrestrial DOM (Williamson *et al.*, 2021). Increased concentrations of iron (Fe), typically accompanying organic carbon, also add to this freshwater browning effect. Fe has strong chromophoric properties in itself with a strong absorption towards lower wavelengths and adds to the light attenuation caused by organic carbon.

Although each link in this chain is well understood, few, if any, studies have tried to run the entire length of the chain, from forest to coastal ecosystems. In a recent project, we explored how increased forest cover, representing increased terrestrial net primary production, can influence distant coastal marine ecosystems. To do this, we used a combination of centennial records of forest and coastal water clarity, contemporary optical measurements in lakes and coastal waters, as well as numerical ocean modelling. This approach quite clearly demonstrated a connection from the growing European forests to decreasing coastal water clarity in the Baltic, Kattegat and Skagerrak Seas, and further, how this brown coloured freshwater

Fig. 3 Predicted phytoplankton response to coastal water darkening {Opal *et al.*, 2019}. This implies a reduction of the euphotic zone, leading to a delayed, intensified, and prolonged spring bloom. While climate warming is suggested to advance the spring bloom due to earlier shoaling of the mixed layer, it also causes browning in lakes and rivers due to increases in terrestrial greening, ultimately reducing water clarity in downstream coastal areas. These contrasting responses highlight the importance of including water transparency in analyses of phytoplankton phenology and primary production in coastal waters.

can be traced across thousands of kilometres along the Norwegian coast where it determines coastal water clarity causing a two week delay of the phytoplankton spring bloom (Fig. 3; Opdal *et al.*, 2023; Opdal *et al.*, 2019).

Interestingly, while climate warming is generally expected to advance the spring bloom due to earlier shoaling of the mixed layer, it also causes browning in lakes and rivers due to increases in terrestrial greening, ultimately reducing water clarity in downstream coastal areas, effectively causing the spring bloom to occur several weeks later (Fig 3; Opdal *et al.*, 2019). In turn, this will likely also influence the timing of copepod reproduction, whose eggs and nauplii larvae are important food for the early life stages of fish, which might well partly explain the delay in cod spawning already observed between 1929 and 1982 in Lofoten, Norway (Pedersen, 1984) and continuing (Opdal *et al.* unpublished data).

Coastal water darkening also poses a range of other ecosystem impacts. Reduced transparency will favour non-visual feeders (*e.g.* jellyfish) at the expense of fish (Eiane *et al.*, 1999), it will likely also affect autotroph communities and also shift systems towards a larger degree of heterotrophy since increased DOC, yet recalcitrant, could serve as a substratum for heterotrophic bacteria while at the same time reduce photosynthetic activity.

As the project continues, we will continue to explore and disentangle these latter links on phytoplankton, copepods and fish spawning with updated data and timeseries. Nonetheless, the findings so far certainly suggest a striking example on ecosystem connectivity from the boreal forest to the Arctic oceans.

References

Aksnes DL, Dupont N, Staby A, Fiksen O, Kaartvedt S, Aure J. 2009. Coastal water darkening and implications for mesopelagic regime shifts in Norwegian fjords. *Marine Ecology Progress Series* 387: 39-49.

Aksnes DL, Utne ACW. 1997. A revised model of visual range in fish. *Sarsia* 82: 137-147

Creed IF, Bergstrom AK, Trick CG, Grimm NB, Hessen DO, Karlsson J, . . . Weyhenmeyer GA. 2018. Global change-driven effects on dissolved organic matter composition: Implications for food webs of northern lakes. *Global Change Biology* 24: 3692-3714.

de Wit HA, Valinia S, Weyhenmeyer GA, Futter MN, Kortelainen P, Austnes K, . . . Vuorenmaa J. 2016. Current browning of surface waters will be further promoted by wetter climate. *Environmental Science & Technology Letters* 3: 430-435.

Eiane K, Aksnes DL, Bagøien E, Kaartvedt S. 1999. Fish or jellies - a question of visibility? *Limnology & Oceanography* 44: 1352-1357.

Finstad AG, Andersen T, Larsen S, Tominaga K, Blumentrath S, de Wit HA, . . . Hessen DO. 2016. From greening to browning: Catchment vegetation development and reduced S-deposition promote organic

carbon load on decadal time scales in Nordic lakes. *Scientific Reports* 6: 31944.

Fransner F, Nycander J, Morth CM, Humborg C, Meier HEM, Hordoir R, . . . Deutsch B. 2016. Tracing terrestrial DOC in the Baltic Sea. A 3-D model study. *Global Biogeochemical Cycles* 30: 134-148.

Karlsson J, Jansson M, Jonsson A. 2007. Respiration of allochthonous organic carbon in unproductive forest lakes determined by the Keeling plot method. *Limnology and Oceanography* 52: 603-608.

Konik M, Darecki M, Pavlov AK, Sagan S, Kowalczyk P. 2021. Darkening of the Svalbard Fjords waters observed with satellite ocean color imagery in 1997-2019. *Frontiers in Marine Science* 8: 699318.

Kritzberg ES, Hasselquist EM, Skerlep M, Lofgren S, Olsson O, Stadmark J, . . . Laudon H. 2020. Browning of freshwaters: Consequences to ecosystem services, underlying drivers, and potential mitigation measures. *Ambio* 49: 375-390.

Martin P, Sanwlani N, Lee TWQ, Wong JMC, Chang KYW, Wong EWS, Liew SC. 2021. Dissolved organic matter from tropical peatlands reduces shelf sea light availability in the Singapore Strait, Southeast Asia. *Marine Ecology Progress Series* 672: 89-109.

Monteith DT, Stoddard JL, Evans CD, de Wit HA, Forsius M... Vesely J. 2007. Dissolved organic carbon trends resulting from changes in atmospheric deposition chemistry. *Nature* 450: 537-U9.

Opdal AF, Andersen T, Hessen DO, Lindemann C, Aksnes DL. 2023. Tracking freshwater browning and coastal water darkening from boreal forests to the Arctic Ocean. *Limnology and Oceanography Letters*. <https://doi.org/10.1002/lol2.10320>

Opdal AF, Lindemann C, Aksnes DL. 2019. Centennial decline in North Sea water clarity causes strong delay in phytoplankton bloom timing. *Global Change Biology* 25: 3946-3953.

Pedersen T. 1984. Variation in peak spawning of Arcto-Norwegian cod (*Gadus morhua* L.) during the time period 1929-1982 based on indices estimated from fishery statistics, p. 301-316. In Dahl E, Daniellssen DS, Moksness E, Solemdal P.[eds.], *The propagation of cod, *Gadus morhua* L.* Flødevigen Rapportserie, Institute of Marine Research.

Thrane JE, Hessen DO, Andersen T. 2014. The absorption of light in lakes: Negative impact of dissolved organic carbon on primary productivity. *Ecosystems* 17: 1040-1052.

Tranvik L, Downing JA, Cotner JB, Loisella SA, Striegl RG... Weyhenmeyer GA. 2009. Lakes and reservoirs as regulators of carbon cycling and climate. *Limnology & Oceanography* 54: 2298-2314

Williamson JL, Tye A, Lapworth DJ, Monteith D, Sanders R, Mayor DJ, . . . Evans C. 2021. Landscape controls on riverine export of dissolved organic carbon from Great Britain. *Biogeochemistry*. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10533-021-00762-2>

<https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8009398>

LIMNOLOGY AROUND THE WORLD: SERBIA

The Danube River in Serbia

**Marija Smederevac-Lalić, Gorčin Cvijanović,
Dušan Nikolić, Milica Jaćimović, Stefan Skorić,
Željka Višnjjić-Jeftić, Aleksandar Hegediš**
Email: marijasmederevac@imsi.rs

University of Belgrade – Institute for Multidisciplinary Research,
Department of Biology and Inland Waters Protection, Belgrade,
Serbia

Over 2850 km long, the Danube River is certainly the most important river in Europe, flowing through Germany (687 km), Austria (358 km), Slovakia (172 km), Hungary (417 km), Croatia (138 km), Serbia (587 km), Bulgaria (472 km), Romania (1075 km), Moldova (<1 km) and Ukraine (54 km) in a west-east direction, and representing a “water backbone” for many European countries located in its basin.

With an average annual flow of about 5,000 m³/s near Belgrade, the Danube River is a significant natural resource, with multipurpose usages along its entire flow, providing extensive ecological services (Fig.1). For example, millions of people in the upper section

Fig. 1 Danube River Island in Belgrade, Great War Island (Zemun) (photo by M. Smederevac-Lalić)

Fig. 2 Tourist cruise ship on the Danube River (photo by M. Smederevac-Lalić)

are supplied with drinking water from this river. Unfortunately, countries in the lower Danube section, usually do not use water from the Danube River, primarily due to pollution. While significant amounts of water from the Danube are also used for irrigation along its course, in Serbia, only about 1.2% of agricultural land is irrigated, or between 40 and 50 thousand hectares (the world average is 17%) (Savić *et al.*, 2013).

Table 1. Protected natural areas along the [Danube River in Serbia](#).

Protected area	Name
National Parks	NP Fruška gora NP Đerdap
Special Nature Reserves	Gornje Podunavlje Karadorđevo Koviljsko – Petrovaradinski rit (wetland) Deliblatska peščara (sand)
Outstanding Natural Landscapes	Forland leve obale Dunava kod Beograda (wetland) Veliko ratno ostrvo (Great War Island) Karaš – Nera
Nature Parks	Tikvara Begečka jama
Monuments of Nature	Lesni profil kod Starog Slankamena Lesni profil Cot Lesni profil Kapela u Batajnici Zemunski lesni profil Ivanovačka ada
Protected Habitats	Veliko blato

Another ecosystem service provided by the Danube is navigation and river traffic (Fig. 2). The Danube is navigable for 2,415 km, from Kelheim to the confluence with the Black Sea. Since 1992, the Rhine-Main-Danube Canal (171 km long Main-Danube Canal) creates a navigable river connection with the North Sea and the Atlantic and Black Sea. This is also important for Serbia since river transport is the cheapest transport and is highly developed in Europe. The most important river ports in Serbia are Novi Sad, Belgrade, Pančevo, Smederevo, and Prahovo (Jolović, 2016).

Like most rivers, the Danube and its tributaries are recipients of waste water along its entire length. Waste waters originate from industry and agriculture, as well as from the numerous cities and settlements it flows through. Much waste is not treated and Serbia’s capital, Belgrade, currently does not have a [wastewater treatment plant](#).

Fig. 3 Petrovaradin Fortress (“The Gibraltar of the Danube”) one of the many fortresses along the Danube River in Serbia. They were engineered as defensive outposts, for navigation security and border patrolling between empires. The cornerstone was laid in 1692 by Charles Eugène de Croÿ (photo by A. Hegediš).

Tourism is certainly one of the most developed economic sectors along entire course of the Danube because of the natural beauty along the river (Figs. 1; 2), safeguarded by the presence of National parks and protected areas. Serbia is no exception, with its numerous cultural and historical monuments, and an abundance of panoramic sights and natural beauty, and cultural-historical monuments (Fig. 3).

The Danube River passes through extraordinary areas rich with biological diversity. For millennia, Danube River was a traffic and

communications corridor, as well as the border of great empires. Today, the Danube with its entire drainage area, connects countries and cultures, and provides a living environment for over 81 million people. As a partial remedy to the many anthropogenic impacts of the last decades, an increasing number of protected areas and natural parks have been instituted. Just in Serbia, there are 17, with different levels of protection measures along the river (Table 1).

Fig. 4 A small Serbian wetland (Pančevački rit) that once characterized vast zones of the Danube floodplain (photo by A. Hegediš).

Many marshes and wetlands that were characteristic of the Danube that flows through the Pannonian Plain have disappeared. Since the 18th century, most wetlands have been drained, and physically separated from the Danube, by fortifying them with defensive embankments, and converting them to agricultural land. To a certain extent, these measures continue, further threatening the remains of the former great wetlands, now reduced to fragments such as: Pančevački rit, Bogojevački rit, Plavna rit- Bačko Novo Selo, Bukinski rit, Koviljsko- Petrovaradinski rit, Dubovački rit, and some smaller flood zones (Fig. 4).

Notwithstanding river and wetland fragmentation, the Serbian part of the Danube with its main branches and floodplain zones is home for 49 different types of aquatic macrophytes (Fig. 5). The most common are: *Ceratophyllum demersum*, *Potamogeton pectinatus*, *Spirodela polyrhiza*, *Rorippa amphibia*, *Potamogeton lucens*, *Butomus umbellatus*, *Potamogeton perfoliatus*, *Potamogeton gramineus*, *Lemna minor*, *Trapa natans*, *Potamogeton nodosus*, *Iris pseudacorus* i *Potamogeton crispus*, while the remaining 36 taxa were detected in less than 20% (Vukov *et al.*, 2017).

The Danube phytoplankton in Serbia is characterized by the absolute dominance of silicate algae (Bacillariophyta), with a total abundance of > 50%, followed by green algae and cryptomonads. Other groups are only present sporadically according to locality and season. This pattern indicates a fairly uniform set of environmental factors in this part of the Danube River (EPA, 2019).

The zooplankton community in the Serbian stretch of the Danube consists of >70 taxa. The most abundant are Rotatoria, with 47 taxa, among which the most common representatives are: *Brachionus* (*B. calyciflorus f. amphiceros*, *B. angularis*, *B. budapestinensis*), *Keratella* (*K. cochlearis*, *K. cochlearis* var. *tecta*), *Polyarthra* (*P. vulgaris*, *P. minor*) and *Trichocerca* (*T. rattus*, *T. pusilla*). Protozoa with 13 taxa are the subdominant group, and the main representatives are: *Carchesium polypinum*, *Vorticella microstoma* and *Stauraphrya elegans*. The planktonic crustaceans Cladocera (9 taxa) and Copepoda (5 taxa) are more abundant in the lower sections of the Danube (downstream from Ritopek). Among the Cladocera, the most common species are *Moina micrura* and *Bosmina longirostris*, and of the Copepoda, the most common species is *Acanthocyclops robustus*. Another very significant component of the zooplankton community, is the larval stage of the non-native invasive mussel *Dreissena polymorpha*, with abundances varying between 6 and 42% (Čađo & Đurković, 2004; Zsuga, 2014).

The Danube and its floodplains is inhabited by a total of 414 taxa of macroinvertebrates from 19 groups, or 33% of the total number of recorded species for Serbia. The most abundant taxa are Diptera,

Oligochaeta, Trichoptera, Odonata, and Gastropoda (68% in total), followed by Ephemeroptera and Bivalvia (13%), while the number of taxa in the remaining 12 groups is smaller (19%) (Petrović, 2014).

The Danube floodplain is a spawning ground for fish, a nesting ground for birds, an area that receives flooding waters and reduces the pressure on embankments, as well as a place where the polluted water is purified and returned to the river at least a class cleaner.

Fig. 5 Some aquatic macrophytes along the Danube in Iron Gate area between two dams, Serbia (photo by M. Smederevac-Lalić).

The list of birds of the floodplain area close to Belgrade is over 120 species. There are also mammals such as deer, rabbits, otters, wild cats, boars.

According to available data, there are 61 fish species in Serbian part of the Danube River. The inland waters of Serbia, which belong to the Black Sea basin, are characterized by a fish fauna dominated by the carp family (*Cyprinidae*). Among the endemics of the Black Sea Basin, you can find the Ballon's ruffe (*Gymnocephalus baloni*), the schraetzer (*Gymnocephalus schraetser*), cactus roach (*Rutilus virgo*) and the salmonid huchen (*Hucho hucho*). Particularly important are six species from the Acipenseridae family. All sturgeons are considered critically endangered species (CR status according to the IUCN), except for the sterlet, which is vulnerable (VU). In

Fig. 6 Sterlet (*Acipenser ruthenus*) (photo by M. Smederevac-Lalić)

Serbia, all sturgeon species are under moratorium. The major threats are more or less the same for migratory Danube sturgeon as for other fish species: overfishing, river flow regulation for flood control, canalization and construction of dams and reservoirs, loss of habitat, introduction of non-native species, water pollution and increase in average water temperatures (Lenhardt *et al.*, 2020). However, the decrease of Danube sturgeon population started with the construction of the Hydropower Iron Gate I and II dams.

For the five Danubian countries, Germany, Austria, Slovakia, Serbia and Romania, the Danube River represents an important energy source. The first hydropower plants in the upper reaches of the river

Table 2. Number of fishermen and catch (tons) for recreational and commercial fishing in Serbia from 2013 – 2021. Data are related to the Danube, Sava and Tisza together, although about 80% of the data refers to the [Danube River](#).

Year	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021
Number of fishermen									
Recreational fishermen (anglers)	77.589	82.750	77.109	77.345	81.944	85.426	88.991	96.001	109.606
Commercial fishermen	511	472	407	408	398	378	443	408	429
Catch (tons)									
From commercial fishing	2.235	908	851	581	590	686	884	761	927
From recreational fishing	2.805	2.683	2.299	1.488	1.618	1.397	1.662	1.170	1.426

were constructed at the end of the XIX century in Germany. Much more important and located on the lower reaches of the Danube are the Hydropower Iron Gate I and II dams that represent the largest hydropower system in Europe, and are jointly managed by Romania and Serbia since the 1970s. Unfortunately, the negative effects of these dams are now obvious. The damming and fragmentation of river flow has caused the loss of the river continuum, thus interrupting the migratory routes of many river organisms, with negative impacts on both aquatic and surrounding terrestrial ecosystems. Habitat loss and fragmentation have especially impacted many economically important fish species (Lenhardt *et al.*, 2020) (Fig. 6).

Migratory routes to spawning areas have been cut off, pollution is increasing, and intensive fishing has continued. This situation led to a rapid decline of populations within a few decades. What was not possible for tens of millions of years and turbulent geological history, glaciations and interglaciations, transgressions and regressions, man succeeded in less than half a century (Hegediš *et al.*, 1994; Kostić *et al.*, 2012; Mičković *et al.*, 1993; Reyjol *et al.*, 2007; Smederevac-Lalić, 2013; Smederevac-Lalić *et al.*, 2017).

Fishing has been a traditional activity in Serbia for centuries (Smederevac-Lalić, 2013). People from the pre-historic Lepenski Vir culture were using fish migrations along Djerdap Gorge as an element for measuring time and entire communities during the Medieval Ages survived thanks to fishing. While there is a still significant level of recreational (Fig. 7) and commercial fishing (Fig. 8) (Table 2), the importance of this activity decreased in the XIX and especially in the XX century (Smederevac-Lalić *et al.*, 2017).

The decline of the Danube fish fauna is due to many anthropogenic impacts, such as unsustainable fishery, river damming, water pollution, dredging, water abstraction and non-native species invasions (Lenhardt *et al.*, 2020). One way to counteract this decline, for example for the migratory shad (*Alosa immaculata*) - considered as a vulnerable species of fish by the IUCN, is to develop forecasting models of catch oscillations to regulate sustainable fishing efforts and species conservation (Smederevac-Lalić *et al.*, 2018).

Historically, there are four sturgeon species in Serbia (beluga sturgeon - *Huso huso*, Russian sturgeon - *Acipenser gueldenstaedtii*, stellate sturgeon - *A. stellatus*, and sterlet - *A. ruthenus*), but sterlet has received the most attention, mainly because it is common potamodromous species. Although protective measures have been tightened and investigation of heavy metals contamination, histopathology and genotoxicity has been done, some basic life

Fig. 8 Commercial fishing on the Danube River in Serbia (photo by M. Smederevac-Lalić).

history traits such as spawning, nursing and wintering habitats, and population status are still unknown. Sturgeon fishing has been banned since 2006 in Romania, followed by Serbia and Bulgaria, but illegal fishing in the Lower Danube is ongoing, and only international cooperation will solve this problem (Lenhardt *et al.*, 2014). Many Danube fish species are in need of conservation efforts. Adequate protection and sustainable management of fish resources in the Danube in Serbia requires introducing an effective monitoring system, establishing and enforcing management plans, and research efforts must be increased on critical issues related to fish management and conservation (Lenhardt *et al.*, 2020).

The best way to ensure that future generations will inherit a healthy Danube is to engage our citizens in its protection and conservation. To do this we promote 'Environmental Citizenship', *i.e.* foster understanding, awareness, and responsible and respectful behaviour towards the environment both as individuals and as a society (Smederevac-Lalić *et al.*, 2020). Environmental Citizenship should be understood as a leading lifestyle that crosses the boundaries of theory and defines responsible personal pro-environmental behavior and practice for citizens. No one starts the day with the idea that one gets up in the morning and decides to intentionally damage the environment, contribute to climate change, water pollution, destruction of the ozone layer, deforestation, etc. What appear to be harmless daily decisions and actions often have far-reaching consequences on the planet. The aim should be to make everyone aware of their ecological footprint (defined as the influence of the everyday activities of every individual person on the planet Earth) through Environmental Citizenship. Acting on a personal level and participating in society through individual and collective actions, in the direction of preventing the creation of new environmental problems, solving environmental problems, achieving sustainability and developing a healthy relationship with nature is the only way towards well-being (Smederevac-Lalić *et al.*, 2020).

References

- Čađo S, Đurković A. 2004. The contents of zooplankton of the Danube River and the saprobiological analysis of water quality. Proceedings of the 2nd Congress of Ecologists of the Republic of Macedonia with International Participation, 25/29 Oct. 2003. Ohrid. Special issues of Macedonian Ecological Society, Skopje. 6: 242–246.
- EPA 2019. Results of surface and underground water quality testing

Fig. 7 Recreational fishing along the Danube River (photo by M. Smederevac-Lalić).

- 2018. Ministry of Environmental Protection, Environmental Protection Agency, Belgrade, 2019. 434 p. [in Serbian] http://www.sepa.gov.rs/download/vode_godisnji_2018.pdf
- Hegediš A, Nikčević M, Mičković B, Andjus RK. 1994. A survey of the fish fauna in floodplains influenced by the Djerdap dam I reservoir. Archives of Biological Sciences 46: 7P-8P.
- Jolović D. 2016. Ten economic contributions of the Danube to Serbia. <http://danube-cooperation.com/danubius/2016/08/18/deset-ekonomskih-doprinosa-dunava-srbiji/> [in Serbian].
- Kostić D, Miljanović B, Lujić J. 2012. The diversity of the fish stock of the Danube from Bezdán to Belgrade. Balkanology Institute of the Serbian Academy of Sciences and Arts, Belgrade. 118: 137 – 151. [in Serbian]
- Lenhardt M, Smederevac-Lalić M, Hegediš A, Skorić S, Cvijanović G, Višnjić Z, Djikanović V, Jovičić K, Jaćimović M, Jarić I. 2020. Human impacts on fish fauna in the Danube River in Serbia: Current status and ecological implications. In Bănăduc D, *et al.*, (eds) Human Impact on Danube Watershed Biodiversity in the XXI Century. Geobotany Studies. Springer.
- Lenhardt M, Smederevac-Lalić M, Djikanović V, Cvijanović G, Vuković-Gačić B, Gačić Z, Jarić I. 2014. Biomonitoring and genetic analysis of sturgeons in Serbia: A contribution to their conservation. Acta Zoologica Bulgarica 66: 69-73.
- Mičković B, Hegediš A, Nikčević M, Andjus RK. 1993. Survey of the fish fauna of the “Djerdap I” reservoir. Archives of Biological Sciences 45: 33P-34P.
- Petrović A. 2014. Possibilities of using the database in the conservation strategy of macroinvertebrates of inland waters at the national level. Doctoral dissertation. Faculty of Science and Mathematics, University of Kragujevac. Kragujevac. 237 pp. [in Serbian]
- Statistical Office of the Republic of Serbia – <https://www.stat.gov.rs/>
- Reyjol Y, Hugueny B, Pont D, Bianco PG, Beier U, Caiola N, Casals F, *et al.* 2007. Patterns in species richness and endemism of European freshwater fish. Global Ecology and Biogeography 16: 65-75.
- Savić R, Pejić B, Ondrašek G, Vranešević M, Bezdán A. 2013. Utilization of natural resources Vojvodina for irrigation. Agroznanje-Agroknowledge Journal 14: 133-142. [in Serbian]
- Smederevac-Lalić M. 2013. Socio-economic and biological characteristics of commercial fishing on the Danube. Doctoral dissertation. University of Belgrade. Belgrade. [in Serbian]
- Smederevac-Lalić M, Kalauzi A, Regner S, Lenhardt M, Naunović Z, Hegediš A. 2017. Prediction of fish catch in the Danube River based on long-term variability in environmental parameters and catch statistics, Science of The Total Environment 609: 664- 671.
- Smederevac-Lalić M, Kalauzi A, Regner S, Navodaru I, Višnjić-Jeftić Ž, Gačić Z, Lenhardt M. 2018. Analysis and forecast of Pontic shad (*Alosa immaculata*) catch in the Danube River. Iranian Journal of Fisheries Sciences 17: 443-457.
- Smederevac-Lalić M, Finger D, Kovách I, Lenhardt M, Petrović J, Djikanovic V, Conti D, Boeve-de Pauw J. 2020. Knowledge and Environmental Citizenship. In: Hadjichambis A. *et al.* (Eds). Conceptualizing Environmental Citizenship for 21st Century Education. Environmental Discourses in Science Education, vol 4. Springer https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-20249-1_5
- Vukov D, Ilić M, Ćuk M, Igić R, Janauer GA. 2017. The relationship between habitat factors and aquatic macrophyte assemblages in the Danube River in Serbia. Archives of Biological Sciences 69: 427 – 437.
- Zsuga K. 2014. Joint Danube Survey 3, Chapter (summary report) on: Zooplankton. ICPDR – International Commission for the Protection of the Danube River. 14 pp.

<https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8009384>

Sunset on the Danube. Photo by M. Smederevac-Lalić

The Tonolli Memorial Fund

The Tonolli Fund of SIL was created in 1985 through a bequest from Vittorio and Livia Tonolli, well known limnologists at the Istituto Italiano di Idrobiologia in Pallanza, Italy. The purpose of the fund is to provide assistance to young limnologists in developing countries and encourage them to join SIL. Information about the fund can be found at LIMNOLOGY.ORG/tonolli-memorial-award. Below is a report from a recent Tonolli Fund recipient.

Argentina

Isolation of pathogenic *Escherichia coli* in two rivers of Argentina

Guillermina Nuozzi^{1,2}, Isabel Chinen³, Elizabeth Miliwebsky³, Julieta Bianchelli⁴, Mara Sagua^{1,2}, María Pía Quiroga^{1,2}, María Romina Schiaffino^{1,2}

¹ Departamento de Ciencias Básicas y Experimentales. Universidad Nacional del Noroeste de la Provincia de Buenos Aires, Argentina.

² Centro de Investigaciones y Transferencia del Noroeste de la Provincia de Buenos Aires (CIT NOBA) UNNOBA-UNSA-CONICET, Argentina.

³ Servicio Fisiopatología, Departamento de Bacteriología. INEI-ANLIS “Dr. Carlos G. Malbrán” Buenos Aires, Argentina.

Email: gnoozzi@comunidad.unnoba.edu.ar

Freshwater systems are threatened by overpopulation, polluted runoff and global warming, resulting in increased nutrient and pollutant inputs (Carbone *et al.*, 2013). This promotes the occurrence of pathogenic microorganisms, inducing the overall deterioration of water quality. In particular, *Escherichia coli* can be detected in elevated densities in human and animal feces, sewage, and waters receiving fecal pollution. *Escherichia coli*'s presence in water indicates the possible existence of fecal pathogens and, consequently, a potential risk to human health (Ishii & Sadowsky, 2008). Some strains of *E. coli* have evolved into highly versatile and frequently deadly pathogens for humans (Barbau-Piednoir *et al.*, 2018), such as Shiga toxin-producing *E. coli* (STEC). Its pathogenicity is related to the production of the Shiga toxin, encoded by the *stx1* and *stx2* genes (*e.g.* Clements *et al.*, 2012). STEC is responsible for Hemolytic Uremic Syndrome, which is endemic in Argentina, with the highest rate of pediatric cases worldwide (Rivas *et al.*, 2014). Other types of diarrheagenic *E. coli* (DEC), including enteropathogenic (EPEC), enterotoxigenic (ETEC), enteroinvasive (EIEC) and enteroaggregative (EAEC) *E. coli*, are harmful to humans, and each is encoded by different genes (Table 1). These categories can cause different degrees of diarrheal diseases in humans depending on the virulence factors involved. Recent studies have shown that the *E. coli* genome has a high plasticity allowing it to adapt to new niches and survive in stressful conditions, (Tanaro *et al.*, 2018) and to evolve into new hybrid strains as new pathotypes (Nyholm, 2016).

Fig. 1: A. Site 2 of Rojas River. B. Site 3 of Salado River.

Fig. 2: Map depicting the rivers selected for this study. A. Selected sites of the Rojas River surrounding Rojas City. B. Selected sites of the Salado River surrounding Junín City. Yellow arrows indicate the direction in which the river flows. S2 in Rojas River and S3 in Salado River (red circle) indicate the location of the wastewater treatment plant. Black arrows indicate the type of DEC found in each site and, between parentheses, the number of each one. S1: site 1, S2: site 2, S3: site 3, S4: site 4. STEC: Shiga toxin-producing *E. coli*, EAEC: enteroaggregative *E. coli*, EPEC: enteropathogenic *E. coli*, EAEC-*lt-st*: enteroaggregative *E. coli* with *lt* and *st* genes.

Table 1. Diarrheagenic *Escherichia coli* and genes that encode each pathotype. STEC: Shiga toxin-producing *E. coli*, EAEC: enteroaggregative *E. coli*, EPEC: enteropathogenic *E. coli*, ETEC: enterotoxigenic *E. coli*, EIEC: enteroinvasive *E. coli*

Diarrheagenic <i>Escherichia coli</i>	Genes
STEC	<i>stx1/stx2/rfbO157</i>
EAEC	<i>aggR/aiiC</i>
EPEC	<i>eae</i>
ETEC	<i>lt/st</i>
EIEC	<i>lpah</i>

The Pampean Region (Argentina) is home to thousands of aquatic systems including rivers, streams and shallow lakes, which are surrounded by agricultural and livestock activities and urban impacts (Quirós *et al.*, 2002). The Salado and Rojas Rivers, located in this region, are impacted by anthropogenic activities since they are located near cities (Junín and Rojas, Province of Buenos Aires, Argentina, respectively) (Fig. 1). We selected four sites in each river based on their proximity to cities: Site 1 (S1) was located upstream of the city, site 2 (S2) and site 3 (S3) near the city, and site 4 (S4) downstream of the city (Fig. 2). We collected samples during March, June, September and December of 2021 and obtained samples suspected of fecal/*E. coli* contamination. The aim of this study was to identify and characterize the *E. coli* strains by detecting specific genes (Table 1) encoding for different virulence factors using multiplex PCR. These genes correspond to different diarrheagenic *E. coli*

strains: STEC, EAEC, EPEC, EIEC and ETEC. A total of eleven pathogenic *E. coli* strains were detected, three isolated from the Rojas River (1 STEC-*stx1/stx2* and 2 EAEC) and eight from the Salado River (1 STEC-*stx2*, 3 EPEC, 3 EAEC and 1 EAEC (*aiiC-st-lt*), as shown in Fig. 2.

The presence of these pathogenic *E. coli* in most of the selected sites in both rivers indicates that anthropogenic activities along the river banks affect the bacterial composition of the water, representing a public health risk. Further studies are needed to elucidate the origin of these bacteria and their survival time in the river. However, the detection of these DEC, together with the abundance of total and thermotolerant coliforms, *E. coli* and environmental data, can provide new basic knowledge about the effect of human activities on the water quality and health of Pampean rivers. Furthermore, the insights gained in this study can provide scientists, policymakers and managers more effective models for the protection, management and restoration of aquatic sites.

Funding

This study was funded by Tonolli Award 2021 by the International Society of Limnology, PICTO 00006-2019 (FONCYT) and SIB 2053-2022 (UNNOBA).

References

Barbau-Piednoir E, Denayer S, Botteldoorn N, Dierick K, De Keersmaecker SCJ, Roosens NH. 2018. Detection and discrimination of five *E. coli* pathotypes using a combinatory SYBR® Green qPCR screening system. *Applied Microbiology and Biotechnology* 102: 3267-

3285.

Carbone ME, García-Martínez B, Marcovechio J, Piccolo M, Perillo G. 2013. Impacto antrópico en la calidad del agua superficial de la cuenca media del Arroyo Claromecó, Argentina. *Cuadernos de Investigación Geográfica*. 39: 391-404.

Clements A, Young JC, Constantinou N, Frankel G. 2012. Infection strategies of enteric pathogenic *Escherichia coli*. *Gut Microbes* 3: 71-87.

Ishii S, Sadowsky MJ. 2008. *Escherichia coli* in the environment: implications for water quality and human health. *Microbes and Environments* 23: 101-108.

Nyholm O. 2016. Virulence variety and hybrid strains of diarrheagenic *Escherichia coli* in Finland and Burkina Faso. *Dissertationes Scholae Doctoralis Scientiae Circumiectalis, Alimentariae, Biologicae*, 23/2016. Faculty of Agriculture and Forestry of the University of Helsinki, Finland.

Quirós R, Rosso J, Rennella A, Sosnovsky A, Boveri M. 2002. Análisis del estado trófico de las lagunas pampeanas (Argentina). *Interciencia* 27: 584-591.

Rivas M, Chinen I, Miliwebsky E, Masana M. 2014. Risk factors for Shiga toxin-producing *Escherichia coli*-associated human diseases. *Microbiology Spectrum* 2(5): 10.1128/microbiolspec.EHEC-0002-2013.

Tanaro JD, Pianciola LA, D'Astek BA, Piaggio MC, Mazzeo ML, Zolezzi G, Rivas M. 2018. Virulence profile of *Escherichia coli* O157 strains isolated from surface water in cattle breeding areas. *Letters in Applied Microbiology* 66: 484-490.

<https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8009426>

Rojas River, Buenos Aires, Argentina. Photo by Guillermina Nuozzi.

FACES of SIL

Björn Wissel

Université Claude Bernard Lyon 1
Lyon, France

BJÖRN WISSEL | FRANCE

My scientific endeavours fall within the scope of Aquatic Systems Ecology. I strive to identify anthropogenic impacts at the ecoregion-scale within the context of watershed controls, hydrology, biogeochemistry, food-web interactions, etc. My study sites have been continental hardwater lakes and boreal lakes in Canada, the Mississippi River- Gulf of Mexico continuum in the United States and, since my move to France, aquaculture ponds in la Dombes (Ain) and their influence on the Saône River. Anthropogenic impacts I have assessed include climate change, industrial emissions, agriculture, pisciculture and urbanization. Beyond quantifying the relative importance of human activities on aquatic systems, I also aspire to identify potential management solutions. Consequently, I have been working closely with government agencies and have started to include Social Sciences into my research. Without understanding human perceptions and behaviours and engaging stakeholders, management approaches are often fruitless. Naturally, these projects ensure that my research is highly collaborative and interdisciplinary in nature to bring together the required expertise.

My vision as General Secretary - Treasurer of SIL is to help build a more diverse and inclusive society that represents limnologists from all backgrounds, origins and walks of life. I am excited about the many new initiatives that our current Board champions to increase accessibility, values, services and visibility of SIL. Stay tuned for many good things to come and reasons to join!

✉ Bjoern.wissel@univ-lyon1.fr

🐦 twitter.com/WisselBjorn

in [björn-wissel-57617a5b](https://www.linkedin.com/in/bjorn-wissel-57617a5b)

Mihir Kulkarni

Laboratory for the Conservation of Endangered Species, CSIR-Centre for Cellular and Molecular Biology, Hyderabad, INDIA

MIHIR KULKARNI | INDIA

I study aquatic invertebrates in India using an evolutionary-ecology framework. First introduced to the wonderful world of zooplankton during my Masters, while assisting with field sampling, I continue to be fascinated by their often overlooked diversity in temporary pools and ponds. After completing my M.Sc. in Zoology, and a stint as a research fellow, I pursued my doctoral research in the Western Ghats in India, where I explored the biodiversity and ecology of freshwater invertebrates over different spatial scales. As a postdoctoral researcher, I currently use molecular methods to study these patterns from an evolutionary perspective.

Facing increasing anthropogenic disturbance and threatened by climate change, freshwater ecosystems in most developing economies are sparsely studied, and India is no exception. Despite its long, complex geo-climatic history, varied topography and rich biodiversity, our knowledge about Indian freshwaters still runs “shallow”. My goal is to contribute to increasing this state of baseline knowledge about freshwater habitats, which is vital for ecosystem-level conservation.

Through my current role as ECR-Developing Countries on the SIL board, I aim to expand networks among limnologists across developing countries through collaborative initiatives and research interactions. I believe that such networks can go a long way in improving the representation of developing countries on the global stage. In the long term, I hope to bring more attention to young researchers in this field by facilitating access to resources for career development. I would be glad to hear any suggestions or ideas from you.

✉ mihir.r.kulkarnii@gmail.com

G <https://scholar.google.com/citations>

RG www.researchgate.net/profile/Mihir-Kulkarni

FACES of SIL

Lena Schallenberg

Cawthron Institute, Hydrosphere Research, New Zealand

LENA SCHALLENBERG | NEW ZEALAND

Hi fellow SIL members, I'm coming to you from down (down) under in New Zealand, a country known for its pristine wilderness and crystal-clear lakes. Growing up around these beautiful freshwaters is what sparked my interest in limnology from a young age (and having a limnologist in the family!). However, freshwaters in New Zealand are also under increasing complex pressures. With agriculture as our biggest industry, land use change along with species invasions and climate change have led to 45% of our lakes currently being in poor or worse condition according to a recent major national [lake surveying/modelling project](#). Now more than ever, learning from mistakes made by older countries including the major restoration efforts (and costs) required after freshwater mismanagement, would hugely benefit our young nation. This, along with incorporating more local mātauranga Māori perspectives and methods would allow us the foresight to be more holistic and preventative in our approach to lake management.

I see SIL playing an important role in helping connect smaller, more isolated countries by acting as a networking hub for limnologists globally. We face many similar challenges, and having open avenues to share and communicate this knowledge widely would be beneficial for the environment and for science. But to successfully provide this, we need to have a solid global networking foundation – something I hope to help build in my new role as Early Career Global Outreach Representative!

✉ lena@hydrosphere.co.nz

Zeynep Ersoy

FEHM-Lab (Freshwater Ecology, Hydrology and Management), Departament de Biologia Evolutiva, Ecologia i Ciències Ambientals, Facultat de Biologia, Universitat de Barcelona, Barcelona, Spain.

ZEYNEP ERSOY | TÜRKİYE/SPAIN

I am an early-career aquatic ecologist currently working as a postdoctoral researcher at the University of Barcelona, Spain. Originally from Türkiye, I have had international experience throughout my career, having worked in Spain, Portugal, Germany, and Denmark. My research primarily focuses on the response of freshwater food webs to climate change and stressors such as eutrophication, salinization, and drought. Specifically, I study changes in community and size structure, biological indices of key elements such as zooplankton, invertebrates, and macrophytes in inland waters ranging from lentic (*i.e.*, lakes, ponds) to lotic (*i.e.*, intermittent rivers), and how these modify ecosystem functioning using large-scale field experiments and biomonitoring surveys.

My interest in aquatic ecology began during my undergraduate studies, where I discovered my passion for fieldwork and observing nature at first hand. As my studies progressed, I became increasingly aware of the fragile state of our ecosystems and the threats they face due to the climate crisis and human activities. This motivated me to work towards protecting these ecosystems in any small way I could, which I believe requires regional and global efforts.

As the VP of Global Outreach Representative for SIL, I will focus on building an inclusive, diverse, and global network of ambassadors to strengthen communication and collaboration between national and regional societies and the SIL Board. I believe that this network will be invaluable in identifying global water issues and developing priorities and solutions for water security and management.

✉ zeynepersoy@gmail.com

🐦 [@zzeynepersoy](https://twitter.com/zzeynepersoy)

🖱️ <https://zeynepersoy.com>

Obituary

Arnold Nauwerck
1931 – 2023

In February 2023 limnologist, colleague, mentor and friend, Prof. Dr. Arnold Nauwerck, passed away.

Born in 1931 in Karlsruhe, he spent his early years in the Black Forest of south-west Germany. He started his studies in Freiburg in the early 1950s before moving to Sweden. His dissertation led to the seminal work entitled *Die Beziehungen zwischen Zooplankton und Phytoplankton im See Erken* (The relationships between zooplankton and phytoplankton in Lake Erken – German with English summary) published in 1963 in Uppsala, bringing him international recognition. He received his doctoral degree in 1962 in Freiburg and his habilitation one year later in Uppsala where he was professor of limnology until 1970. During those years he was guest professor in Innsbruck, invited by his friend Roland Pechlaner, and went on a six-month expedition to Central Africa. He moved on to Canada, to the Centre of Inland Waters in Burlington, Ontario, studying plankton productivity in the Great Lakes. In 1973 he returned to Sweden and worked as department head for air and water pollution surveillance in the provincial government of Norrbotten, until 1987. During those years he also worked as a lecturer at the University of Innsbruck and at the Luleå University of Technology.

He was nominated Director of the Institute for Limnology of the Austrian Academy of Sciences (consisting of the departments in Mondsee and in Lunz) in 1987 which he led for 10 years until retiring in 1997. He closely cooperated with his friend Gernot Bretschko, head of the department in Lunz. Scientifically he focused on trophic relationships between phytoplankton, zooplankton and fish and generally on the stability of aquatic ecosystems as well as the adaptation of aquatic organisms. Teaching was an important part of his activities and he was promoted to honorary professor at the University of Salzburg. His activities in developing and teaching the *International Post-Graduate Course in Limnology* led to many foreign collaborations, e.g. the Makerere University in Uganda, Egerton University in Kenya and Academia Sinica in Nanjing, China. He was a member of several committees such as the steering group forming the Institute of Freshwater Ecology and Inland Fisheries (IGB) in Berlin and the scientific advisory board of the Institute of Hydrobiology of the Czech Academy of Sciences in České Budějovice. From the latter institution he was awarded the Gregor Mendel Medal in 1998. Furthermore, he was a member of the editorial boards for the journals *Aqua Fennica*, *Annales de Limnologie* and *Limnologica*. His scientific legacy includes more than 100 publications of limnological content which has inspired and will inspire future generations of limnologists.

[Josef Wanzenböck](#)

Research Department for Limnology Mondsee
University of Innsbruck, Mondseestraße 9, A-5310 Mondsee
Austria

Selected publications:

Vollenweider RA, Nauwerck A. 1961. Some observations on the C14 method for measuring primary production. *Verhandlungen des Internationalen Verein Limnologie* 14: 134-139.

Nauwerck A. 1963. Die Beziehungen zwischen Zooplankton und Phytoplankton im See Erken. *Symbolae botanicae upsalienses* 17(5): 1-163 (pdf available from J. Wanzenböck).

Nauwerck A. *et al.* 1980. Chapters 5 & 6 - Primary production and Secondary production. In: Le Cren ED, Lowe-McConnel RH. (eds.) *The Functioning of Freshwater Ecosystems*, IBP Program 22, Cambridge University Press.

Nauwerck A. 1991. Zooplankton changes in Lake Mondsee. *Verhandlungen der Internationalen Vereinigung für Limnologie* 24: 974-979.

Nauwerck A. 1991. The history of the genus *Eubosmina* in Lake Mondsee (Upper Austria). *Hydrobiologia* 225: 87-103.

Kizito YS, Nauwerck A. 1995. Temporal and vertical distribution of planktonic rotifers in a meromictic western Uganda crater lake, Lake Nyahirya. *Hydrobiologia* 313/314: 303-312.

Miao S, Nauwerck A. 1999. Fungal infection of *Eudiaptomus gracilis* (Copepoda, Crustacea) in Lake Mondsee. *Limnologica* 29: 168-173.

Further reading:

Schiemer F. 2014. [A short history of limnology in Austria](#). *Denisia* 33: 33-59. [in German with English summary]

SIL Officers 2024-2025

PRESIDENT

Thomas Mehner

mehner@igb-berlin.de

Leibniz-Institute of Freshwater Ecology and Inland Fisheries (IGB)
Dept. of Biology and Ecology of Fishes
Mueggelseedamm 310
Berlin
GERMANY

GENERAL SECRETARY-TREASURER

Björn Wissel

bjoern.wissel@univ-lyon1.fr

Laboratoire d'Écologie des Hydrosystèmes Naturels et Anthropisés
UMR 5023
Université Claude Bernard Lyon 1
Bâtiment Forel - 6 rue Raphaël Dubois
69622 Villeurbanne Cedex
FRANCE

EXECUTIVE VICE PRESIDENT DEVELOPING COUNTRIES

Inés O'Farrell

ines@ege.fcen.uba.ar

National Council of Scientific and Technological Research of Argentina (CONICET)
Institute of Ecology, Genetics and Evolution of Buenos Aires
Buenos Aires
ARGENTINA

STUDENT/EARLY CAREER REPRESENTATIVE - DEVELOPING COUNTRIES

Dr. Mihir Kulkarni

mihircoolkarni@gmail.com

Student/Early Career Representative- Developing Countries
Laboratory for Conservation of Endangered Species
CSIR- Center for Cellular and Molecular Biology
Hyderabad
INDIA

EXECUTIVE VICE PRESIDENT - COMMUNICATION

Cecilia Barouillet

cecilia.barouillet@gmail.com

INRAE, 75bis Avenue de Corzent
CS 50511
Thonon les bains, 74200
FRANCE

STUDENT/EARLY CAREER REPRESENTATIVE - COMMUNICATION

Juan David González Trujillo

jdgonzalez@gmail.com

Rui Nabeiro Biodiversity Chair
MED Institute
Universidade de Évora
PORTUGAL

EXECUTIVE VICE PRESIDENT - EDUCATION

Maria de los Angeles Gonzalez Sagrario

gonsagra@mdp.edu.ar

IIMYC-CONICET
Derqui 147 PB A, Mar del Plata
Buenos Aires, 7600
ARGENTINA

STUDENT/EARLY CAREER REPRESENTATIVE - EDUCATION

Barbara Barta

barta.barbara@ecolres.hu

Centre for Ecological Research
Institute of Aquatic Ecology
Karolina út 29, Budapest, 1113
HUNGARY

SIL Officers 2024-2025

**EXECUTIVE VICE PRESIDENT -
GLOBAL OUTREACH**

Dr. Zeynep Ersoy

zzeynepersoy@gmail.com

FEHM-Lab (Freshwater Ecology,
Hydrology and Management)
Section of Ecology, Department of
Evolutionary Biology
Ecology and Environmental Sciences
University of Barcelona
Barcelona
SPAIN

**STUDENT/EARLY CAREER
REPRESENTATIVE -
GLOBAL OUTREACH**

Dr. Lena Schallenberg

lenaschall@hotmail.com

University of Otago
Department of Zoology
Dunedin
NEW ZEALAND

EDITOR, INLAND WATERS

David Hamilton

david.p.hamilton@griffith.edu.au

Australian Rivers Institute
Sir Samuel Griffith Centre (N78)
170 Kessels Road
Nathan Campus, QLD 4111
AUSTRALIA

EDITOR, SILnews

Giovanna Flaim

SILnews@limnology.org

Fondazione Edmund Mach
38010 San Michele all'Adige
Trento
ITALY

SIL WEBMASTER

Veronica Nava

webmaster@limnology.org

University of Milano-Bicocca
Department of Earth
and Environmental Sciences
Piazza della Scienza 1
20126 Milano
ITALY

**MEMBERSHIP and
COMMUNICATIONS
COORDINATOR**

Michelle Gros

Business@limnology.org

International Society of Limnology
c/o UQAM
P.O. Box 8888, succ. Centre-Ville
Montreal, QC
CANADA H3C 3P8

SIL BUSINESS MANAGER

Genevieve Leclerc

business@limnology.org

International Society of Limnology
c/o UQAM
P.O. Box 8888, succ. Centre-Ville
Montreal, QC
CANADA H3C 3P8

SILnews (ISSN 2707-9422) is the official newsletter of SIL (International Society of Limnology @ limnology.org) and is published online twice yearly in January and July (<https://limnology.org/publications/sil-news/-online>). International Society of Limnology c/o UQAM - P.O. Box 8888, succ. Centre-Ville Montreal, QC, CANADA H3C 3P8. Business Manager Genevieve Leclerc; Editor Giovanna Flaim. Disclaimer - The opinions expressed in this publication are those of the authors and do not necessarily reflect the opinions or views of SIL or its members.